

Adaptive Gating for Heterogeneous Graph Transformers

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Abstract

Heterogeneous Graph Transformers (HGT) have been a popular architecture for learning heterogeneous structured datasets. However, they can still suffer from over-smoothing or the lack of strength of filtering irrelevant neighbor information in layers. In this study, we propose the Gated Heterogeneous Graph Transformer (G-HGT), an extension of HGT, where it introduces a trainable GRU-inspired gating system to flexibly adjust information input at nodes during message passing. This gate behaves like a flexible information bottleneck, where it adds up prior node states with new heterogeneous messages through a continuous gate variable, being between 0 and 1. This will let the model to keep meaningful information while discarding irrelevant information. We used DBLP heterogeneous network as our evaluation dataset, comprising of four node types (Author, Paper, Term, Venue) and a 4-class author classification task. Although G-HGT does not outperform HGT on the clean DBLP dataset, our further analyses show that the learned gates selectively suppress some of the messages, highlighting its potential value in noisier dataset. G-HGT achieves lower accuracy of 82%, compared with standard HGT. We conducted additional analyses to highlight whether the gating system is performing as expected or not. Analysis of gate activations highlights an average value of 0.40, with standard deviation of 0.27, highlighting that the model selectively filters a substantial portion of incoming messages rather than collapsing into redundant behavior. This, itself, could be related to handling over-smoothing. Also Mean gate activation per node type highlight that the gating is selectively discarding some messages while accepting others. These findings suggest that G-HGT provides a valid mechanism for mitigating over-smoothing and may offer greater advantages on noisier or higher-density heterogeneous graphs. Future work will explore scaling the gating mechanism to different architectures.

Keywords: Gated Message Passing, Message Filtering, Over-smoothing, Noise-robust Learning, Node Classification

Introduction

Heterogeneous information network (HIN) incorporate various types of objects (e.g., nodes) and different relationship (edge) [1]. They are common in various fields from citation network [2, 3], recommendation system [4, 5], and social network [6, 7]. The data incorporated in this study could also be represented as HIN, consisting of three types of (e.g., papers, author, subject), and various types of edge or relationships (e.g., author-write-paper).

Traditional graph neural network (GNN) has been found strong in handling homogeneous graph, which contain only a single type of node and edge [2, 7, 8]. However, real life examples of data include various nodes and edges types. This has resulted in HIN to gain traction due to, using representation learning. That lead to the development of a GNN known as heterogeneous graph neural network (HGNN), which are able to design the richer structure.

Relational Graph Convolutional Network (R-GCN), as a representative model within the broader family of heterogeneous graph neural networks (HGNNs), has extended traditional graph convolution network (GCN) by incorporating relation specific weight to account for diverse relationship within an HIT [7]. Despite the success of the HGNNs, the limitation exist such as over-smoothing [9], and over squashing [10].

Heterogeneous transformer -like attention architectures, such as the Heterogeneous Graph Transformer (HGT), were proposed for improvement of neighbor aggregation [11]. Additional variant such as HINormer, implementing local structure encoder and a heterogeneous relation encoder, were employed to capture heterogeneity information in HIN [12]. However, it was discussed the limitation of the HGN, and the modification was proposed by means of Hierarchical Heterogeneous Graph Transformer (HHGT) to address the limitations of those HGT approaches to prevent mixing nodes of different types and also treating all nodes within k -hop neighborhood during neighbor aggregation, and potentially preventing potential semantic confusion [13].

Study contributions

While gating mechanisms have been explored in several GNN variants, such as Gated Graph Neural Networks (GGNN) by using Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) [15], Gated Attention Networks (GAAN) by introducing attention gating [16], and GeniePath by employing depth gating [17], to the best of knowledge, none of these methods integrate a learnable gate directly into the heterogeneous message-passing update of HGT. This gap might be important as HGT relies on residual connections which will always add new messages, regardless of their relevance. Thus, HGT cannot suppress noisy or uninformative neighbor information, which may worsen oversmoothing in deeper layers

This work proposed the Gated Heterogeneous Graph Transformer (G-HGT), a modification of HGT incorporating a GRU-inspired gating mechanism into the node update rule. Unlike the standard HGT, using a fixed residual connection, G-HGT is in the range of $[0,1]$. That means the process flexibly adds the previous node states with new heterogeneous messages. This provides a

trainable information bottleneck which could filter out irrelevant messages while keeping meaningful node identity. In this study, we evaluate G-HGT on the DBLP heterogeneous network and analyze gate activations to better understand how the model integrates information selectively.

Methodology

The core part of this work is the implementation of the G-HGT update so it is worth discussing its implementation versus the standard HGT. In both HGT and G-HGT, after feature projection layers, the main operation is related to HGTCnv, or standard HGT, which aggregate and transform messages from its neighbors based on heterogenous attention. The following passages of this sections explain a standard HGT first and then elaborate on its extension to G-HGT.

The HGTCnv is a critical part of the heterogenous graph transformer (HGT) architecture, performing both message passing and attention for aggregating information across diverse neighbors [11]. This standard HGT section is based on the original performed work [11]. The whole processes of standard HGT could be divided into 1-node and edge-type specific projection. 2-heterogenous attention, 3- message aggregation, and 4- node update (aggregation of all message types). It should be noted that all of these steps will be implemented internally and the innovative gating mechanism will be implemented at the latter stage.

1- in the first step, HGT projects nodes features and then transfers each node and edge type into a common embedding space. This will ensure that different nodes, like authors and papers in this paper, can be combined appropriately.

Here nodes will be transformed as

$$h_i^\tau = W_{node}^\tau h_i^\tau \tag{1}$$

Where:

h_i^τ is the original feature vector of node i of type τ .

W_{node}^τ is a trainable weight, or projection matrix, of node type τ .

$h_i^{|\tau}$ is the projected feature vector of node i into the common embedding space.

On the other hand, rather than use of raw node features, the source node features based on the type of relationship that it has with target node, and through edge type will be transformed for message formation

$$V_j^\omega = W_V^\omega h_j^{(\omega)}$$

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Where:

V_j^ω : projected value vector for node j , this is what gets aggregated in message passing;

i : target node index

j : Source (neighbor) index

$h_j^{(\omega)}$: original feature vector of node j of type ω .

W_V^ω : learnable value projection matrix for node type ω .

2- Heterogenous attention: HGT uses transformer-style attention process similar to the previous study, defining Q , K and V [20]. HGT, uses node-type-specific projections and relation-specific transformations. The process could be written as:

$$Q_i^\tau = W_Q^\tau h_i^{(\tau)} \quad 3$$

$$K_j^\omega = W_K^\omega h_j^{(\omega)} \quad 4$$

$$V_j^\omega = W_V^\omega h_j^{(\omega)} \quad 5$$

$$Att(i, j) = \frac{(Q_i^\tau) W^{(\Phi)} K_j^\omega}{\sqrt{d}} \quad 6$$

where:

j : source (neighbor) node index,

ω : node type of node j ,

$W_Q^\tau \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$: query projection for node type τ ,

$W_K^\omega \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$: key projection for node type ω ,

$W_V^\omega \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$: value projection for node type ω ,

$Q_i^\tau \in \mathbb{R}^d$: query vector of node i ,

$K_j^\omega \in \mathbb{R}^d$: key vector of node j ,

$V_j^\omega \in \mathbb{R}^d$: value vector of node j ,

Subsequently, SoftMax across neighbor will be used to normalize the attention score as:

$$\alpha_{ij}^{(\tau, \omega)} = \text{Softmax}_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^\omega} (Att(i, j))$$

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Where:

\mathcal{N}_i^ω : set of neighbors of node i with type ω

$\alpha_{ij}^{(\tau,\omega)}$: normalized attention weight

3. Message aggregation:

For HGT model, message aggregation describes how a target node collects and aggregate information from its heterogeneous neighbors, which is also weighted by the learned attention scores.

$$M_i^{(\omega \rightarrow \tau)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^\omega} \alpha_{ij}^{(\tau,\omega)} W_V^{(\phi)} V_j^\omega \quad 8$$

target node i , node being updated,

ω — node type of the source node,

τ — node type of the target node,

\mathcal{N}_i^ω — neighbors of node i that are of type ω ,

$\alpha_{ij}^{(\tau,\omega)}$ attention weight from node j to node i ,

V_j^ω — value vector of source node j ,

$W_V^{(\phi)}$ — relation-specific value transformation (depends on edge type ϕ),

$M_i^{(\omega \rightarrow \tau)} \in \mathbb{R}^d$: aggregated message from neighbors of all type ω to node i ,

Each neighbor contributes proportionally to its attention weight

4- node update (aggregation of all message types)

At the end, and after computing the messages from each neighbor type, HGT messages from all neighbors will be aggregated to form a new node representation.

$$h_i^{(\tau, new)} = ReLU\left(\sum_{w \in \mathcal{J}_i} M_i^{w \rightarrow \tau} + h_i^{(\tau)}\right) \quad 9$$

Where:

T_i : set of node types connected to node i

$\sum_{\omega \in T_i}$: aggregation across all message types

$M_i^{\omega \rightarrow \tau}$ — aggregated message from neighbors of type ω

$h_i^{(\tau)}$: residual (skip connection) from the original representation of node

$\text{ReLU}(\cdot)$: non-linear activation function

$h_i^{(\tau, \text{new})}$: updated node representation after combining all message types

Here h_i^τ acts as a residual connection, adding the initial transformed features of node i to the aggregated message before the state of the final activation. It should be noted that internally, each HGT layer performs the residual connection. Then, that node representation would be turned into prediction score for research areas and these logits will be compared against the true labels.

In other words, the standard HGT often used residual connection for updating node feature. Consider x_t as the node's representation at layer t , and $HGTConv(x_t)$ as the aggregated message from its neighbors, now the update rule could be written as, which will be followed by Relu:

$$x_{t+1} = \text{Activation}(x_t + HGTConv(x_t)) \quad 10$$

The above equation means that the new message will be always integrated without a learnable mechanism for filtering its influence and will be directly added to the previous state.

5- G-HGT

Now, turning to our implemented of G—HGT, which uses a learnable gate z , which manage the blend between the old stage x_t and the new message generated by HGTConv layer. That will be often followed by a ReLU activation. The update rule for G-HGT could be written as:

$$x_{t+1} = (1 - z) \odot x_t + z \odot \text{Activation}(HGTConv(x_t)) \quad 11$$

Here x_t is the node's representation before the $t+1$ layer. z is the output of the learnable implemented gate with a value between 0 and 1. \odot is element-wise multiplication. Activation is typically a ReLU activation being applied to the new message.

Here the output of our learnable gating process is computed by concatenating the old state and a new message as:

$$z = \sigma(\text{Linear}(x_t \parallel HGTConv(x_t))) \quad 12$$

Where

σ producing values in $[0,1]$

$HGTConv(x_t)$ is the new message from heterogeneous neighbors and x_t is the previous node representation.

In this work, the change was the addition of the term of $(1 - z) \odot x_t$, instead of simply addition of the new messages, where the process learns for each node and its types, and how much of its previous state to retain and how much of the new information to get incorporated.

Few points should be highlighted regarding equation 11, if z is low, the node will ignore the incoming message while preserving its local identity. On the other hand, if z is high, the model turns into a standard HGT, where it will fully integrate the new information. In summary, the process helps the nodes to keep distinct representation even in deeper networks, while the model mitigates the over-smoothing problem common in GNN.

It should be noted, in this work, the G-HGT does residual connection by learned control. Similar to the following equation:

$$out_{dict}[node_{type}] = (1 - z) \times out_{dic}[node_{type}] + z \times new_out_dic[node_{type}].relu() \quad 13$$

Where $out_{dic}[node_{type}]$ on the right-hand side represents the old state (the direct pass-through or residual part). $new_out_dic[node_{type}].relu()$, on the other hand, represents the transformed version of the new message. Lastly, as we discussed before, gates $1 - z$ and z learn to blend how much of the old state to retain and how much of the new message to use. This could be called as a more adoptive way for managing the information, compared with simple additive residuals.

In both HGT and G-HGT, edges are playing a significant rule. They highlight how nodes are connected for each relation type. During message passing, the numerical edge index tells the model which source nodes send information to which target nodes. For both models, query, key, and value vectors will be created based on node types, and consequently applies relation-specific transformations. Then multi-head attention will be implemented to combine messages. In both models, residual connections and normalization provide support in stabilizing the updates. The final outcome allows HGT to learn the different meanings of each relation, while keeping the overall structure of the heterogeneous graph.

Experimental Setup

This section will elaborate on the selections of hyperparameters for both HGT and G-HGT. The choice of the selections of these parameters are based on established common practice in implementation of GNN, our observation while training various models, and also the original published paper about HGT. These choices also reflected the computational limitations while running the models.

Hidden channels clarify how many dimensional layers we want to translate our node type to. For instance, we have various types of papers, authors, venue types, where all will be transformed

into 128 embedding sizes. 128 provides sufficient complexity to learn the representation of those node. Edges types act as a learnable entity that specialized in message passing and they impact how nodes enhance their representation.

Numbers of attention heads was set as 4 attention heads within each HGTCConv layer. 4 heads allow the model to learn various aspects of relational information simultaneously. That helps the model to learn diverse pattern from graph structure.

Numbers of layers was set as two layers for capturing 2 hop dependency and we did not increase number of layers/hop to prevent a common over smoothing issue of HGT. The models were trained over 300 epochs for allowing both architectures enough time to converge. Gated architecture in general needed more warm up time and longer optimization time for convergence compared with a standard HGT, which has a simpler residual connection. However, for conducting a fair comparison, numbers of epoch were set identically across both models.

Finally, regarding optimizer, we used the Adam optimizer for training. A learning rate of 0.001 was used to keep a right balance across speed and stability. We also penalized a large weight for prevention of overfitting by means of L2 or weight decay, with a value of $5e-4$.

In this study, existing train and test split used for the DBLP dataset. We use `train_mask` and `test_mask` on the 'author' nodes for our model training and prediction. it should be noted that due the absence of an explicit validation split we did not employ any validation data.

Data

Digital Bibliography & Library Project (DBLP) data is publicly available data that have been used for modeling heterogenous graph for various tasks such as node classifications. That is particularly suitable for HGT. The data include 4 nodes of author (including 4057 node), paper (14,328), term (7,723), venue (20). In that data the author node is represented by 334-dimensional feature vector x . The primary task is to classify authors into four research areas with a mask for training and test data.

Paper, on the other hand, has a dimensional size of 4231, with its content-related information. The feature vector of terms and venue are 50 and 20, respectively. The graph incorporates various edge types including (author, to, paper which means author wrote a paper), (paper, to, term), (paper, to, venue), (paper, to, author), (term, to, paper) and (venue, to, paper). The objective is 4-node classification task on author including Category 0: Database, 1: Data Mining, 2: AI, and the last one as Information Retrieval

Results

The results section will be presented in three subsections by means of 3 figures. The inclusion of 3 figures proposed to evaluate Gated Heterogeneous Graph Transformer (G-HGT) against the standard HGT model. Those three figures are especially important to include to illustrate

performance and the inner workings of the gating mechanism. Together, the analyses aim to provide insight into G-HGT's adaptive learning process.

Training process

Fig 1 is presented to highlight the training process of the standard HGT and G-HGT over 300 epochs. As can be seen from Fig 1, HGT reached and stabilize much faster compared with G-HGT. This slower convergence indicates that G-HGT might need more signal at the training stage or maybe more sensitive to the characteristics of the dataset. Further analyses are provided in the following subsections to better understand the behaviors of the G-HGT.

Figure 1. Training trajectory of HGT vs G-HGT

Figure 2 highlights the mean gate activation per node type, showing how the gating mechanism works across various layers and features. This visualization helps to understand whether the model selectively filters information for different categories of node as an example. This distribution provides a view of how strongly the gating mechanism could suppress or amplify information within a specific node type.

Together, Figures 2 and 3 could confirm whether the gating mechanism is behaving as intended, in other words, whether it learns to control information flow rather than passing all features uniformly.

Mean gate activation per node type

Fig 2 reports the mean gate activation for each node type across layers, providing an evidence of how the gating mechanism control information flow at the feature level. A high z value highlights the strong integration of the new info, while low z means the model selectively filters some of the input of the model, look at Equation 13. The results of the figure could highlight the adaptability of our gate in selection or discarding the information.

The process starts by initially mapping features into a common embedding space, while handling featureless node like venue with learned embedding. To process gate input, we concatenate the node previous state with the current state, look at Equation 12. Then calculating the gate, z , value, using the node-type specific gating network, outputting a value between 0 and 1. Store the average of z values for the current node. Then we apply the gated update rule $(1-z) \times \text{old_state} + z \times \text{relu}(\text{new_message})$

Based on Equation 11 and from Fig 2 the gate mean value around 0.4 indicates that on average, the gated model is selectively filtering a significant proportion of the incoming messages from neighbors. This value of below 0.50 means that gate tends to retain more of the current messages, and discard the majority of the neighbor message, especially for author at both layers.

Figure 2. Mean gate activation per node type

Distribution of gate values for author nodes

Based on the above figure, to further confirm the assumption that gates are not collapsed at the two-extreme spectrum of near 0 and 1, Fig 3 provides further information to visualize how the distribution of the gates vary. Across author node. This distribution provides a finer view of how the gating network behaves beside the mean activations reported earlier.

As can be seen from Fig 3, the high variance of 0.3 means that the gate values are spread out across spectrum from 0 to 1, highlighting the gating process is not redundant, for instance it did not assign a very high value to every node. Average of 0.4 means that the model is currently on average blocking 60% of the information flow.

Figure 3. distribution of gate value (z) for author nodes, mean of 0.41, Var of 0.271

Discussion

One of the challenges associated with standard HGT is its inability to discard irrelevant or noisy information potentially degradation of the model performance. However, the gated HGT addresses that by blocking irritant messages from the neighbor nodes.

In this paper, we introduced a novel gating technique designed to filter irrelevant information. Under condition of noisy or irrelevant information, the gating processes plays a rule by discarding irrelevant and noisy information while keeping important ones. The process is served as an enhancement of standard HGT by employing an update rule which acts as a gating process for keeping only relevant information during message passing.

To put a context into our comparison, we incorporated additional analyses showing that gate process is acting as intended and the lower accuracy of the gated model could be attributable to the used dataset rather than the failure of the methodological approach itself. evaluated the model on a single dataset, where standard HGT outperform the G-HGT. To put that outcome in

context, we included additional analyses showing that the gating process is acting as intended and as lower accuracy result might be attributable to the cleanness and structure of the used dataset. Figure 1 presents the accuracy trajectories of both models.

Gated-HGT's accuracy is lower and converges to a lower final value compared with the standard model. As can be seen, Fig 1 shows a more gradual increase over the 300 epochs. Also as could be seen Gated-HGT begins with slower progress, but it continues improving throughout training, reaching approximately 82% accuracy by epoch 300.

However, the standard HGT plateaus much earlier, reaching 94% around epoch 100 and stabilize thereafter, where it reaches about 94% by epoch 100 and then stabilize after that point. This might highlight that the Gated-HGT still adjusting its parameters and gating behavior over a longer training time.

Longer training time for G-HGT could indicate that the model needs additional iterations to refine its selective filtering behavior, although the benefits of this process may not show itself on a relatively simple or clean dataset. Another issue to take into consideration for HGT is the possibility of over-smoothing. Although for the current employed clean dataset, this effect is unlikely to appear, G-HGT shows steadier learning dynamics, suggesting more controlled message passing without large fluctuations.]

The current dataset, as a relatively clean dataset, did not reveal the advantage of the G-HGT. That could be highlighted from the lower accuracy of Gated-HG. However, that does not indicate model failure; rather, it suggests that the model's strengths are not fully utilized on a the employed highly structured and noise-free dataset.

It should be noted that the additional computational burden of G-HGT arises not from raw cost but from the need to update both node representations and gating parameters through its adaptive control mechanism.

Gate Behavior

We presented the mean gate activation per node type to illustrate how much of the new messages from neighbors are filtered. Our current results show that the gating model tends to keep more of the existing state, rather than letting new information in. Also, the warm-up stage of the figure highlights that G-HGT continues adapting its gating behavior, whereas HGT converges rapidly.

To further confirm the performance of our model and ensure the model is not potentially performing at extreme points of the spectrum, we also include the distribution plot of gate values (z) for author nodes. The distribution shows that the gate adaptively modulates incoming information instead of behaving unexpectedly or collapsing to trivial values.

Summary

In summary, the standard HGT reaches a higher accuracy of 94% vs. 82% for G-HGT. However, our post-hoc analyses indicates that this difference could be mostly attributable to the relatively

clean nature of the DBLP dataset. Although HGT performed better than the gated version, the empirical analyses indicate that Gated-HGT is more suitable for noisier datasets.

In those conditions, the model potentially filter irrelevant information to keep its distinct node representations. It is likely also the adaptive gating mechanism makes the model well-fitted for filtering irrelevant information, a characteristic that is critical when working with noisy or heterogeneous data sources.

As we discussed here, compared with standard HGT which employed, a binary choice mechanism, the G-HGT gate z assigns a continuous weight between 0 and 1 turning that into messages. Figure 2 highlights mean gate activation per node type, showing how the gate works for each feature within each layer, highlighting the model's selective filtering behavior.

Figure 3, on the other hand shows the distribution of gate values for author nodes. As discussed the reason for including both Figures 2 and 3 was to verify that the gating mechanism behaves as intended.

References

1. Sun, Y. and J. Han, *Mining heterogeneous information networks: a structural analysis approach*. ACM SIGKDD explorations newsletter, 2013. **14**(2): p. 20-28.
2. Hamilton, W., Z. Ying, and J. Leskovec, *Inductive representation learning on large graphs*. Advances in neural information processing systems, 2017. **30**.
3. Wang, D., P. Cui, and W. Zhu. *Structural deep network embedding*. in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*. 2016.
4. Berg, R.v.d., T.N. Kipf, and M. Welling, *Graph convolutional matrix completion*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1706.02263, 2017.
5. Zhang, J., et al., *Star-gcn: Stacked and reconstructed graph convolutional networks for recommender systems*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1905.13129, 2019.
6. Atwood, J. and D. Towsley, *Diffusion-convolutional neural networks*. Advances in neural information processing systems, 2016. **29**.
7. Kipf, T.N. and M. Welling, *Semi-supervised classification with graph convolutional networks*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1609.02907, 2016.
8. Dai, E., et al. *Towards robust graph neural networks for noisy graphs with sparse labels*. in *Proceedings of the fifteenth ACM international conference on web search and data mining*. 2022.
9. Chen, D., et al. *Measuring and relieving the over-smoothing problem for graph neural networks from the topological view*. in *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*. 2020.
10. Alon, U. and E. Yahav, *On the bottleneck of graph neural networks and its practical implications*. arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.05205, 2020.

11. Hu, Z., et al. *Heterogeneous graph transformer*. in *Proceedings of the web conference 2020*. 2020.
12. Mao, Q., et al. *Hinormer: Representation learning on heterogeneous information networks with graph transformer*. in *Proceedings of the ACM web conference 2023*. 2023.
13. Zhu, Q., et al. *Hhgt: hierarchical heterogeneous graph transformer for heterogeneous graph representation learning*. in *Proceedings of the Eighteenth ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining*. 2025.
14. Scarselli, F., et al., *The graph neural network model*. *IEEE transactions on neural networks*, 2008. **20**(1): p. 61-80.
15. Li, Y., et al., *Gated graph sequence neural networks*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1511.05493, 2015.
16. Zhang, J., et al., *Gaan: Gated attention networks for learning on large and spatiotemporal graphs*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1803.07294, 2018.
17. Liu, Z., et al. *Geniepath: Graph neural networks with adaptive receptive paths*. in *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*. 2019.
18. Xu, K., et al., *How powerful are graph neural networks?* arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.00826, 2018.
19. Wu, Z., et al., *Graph wavenet for deep spatial-temporal graph modeling*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.00121, 2019.
20. Vaswani, A., et al., *Attention is all you need*. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 2017. **30**.